
1. Overview of Data Augmentation

Southern Cross University

SQL queries are used in SCU's integrated research management application to produce two key outputs:

1. **Grants Output:** This details research grants, their investigators, associated fund providers and amounts.
2. **Researchers Output:** This provides information about researchers, including their identifiers and fields of research.

Both outputs are designed to facilitate information sharing and collaboration across research sectors via **Research Link Australia**.

Griffith University

Griffith University data is stored in the Research Information Management Systems (RIMS). Using the RIMS reporting functionality, tables were queried for the relevant fields as defined by the Master RLA Proposed Data Fields Partner Feasibility Statements.

Prior to any data augmentation against Grant and Researcher fields, it was necessary to remove confidential information from these research data holdings.

1. Removal of data deemed confidential at each record:
 - a. All rows where *project_type* column contains 'Confidential'
 - b. All rows where the embargoed column value equals 'Yes'.
2. Removal of grants information that was not simultaneously published on Griffith Experts.

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Grants and researcher information from UTS Symplectic Elements derived using API and SQL queries:

1. **Grants** - This includes details on research grants:
 - a. funding providers
 - b. investigators
 - c. funding amounts

- d. grant title
 - e. funding type and scheme
 - f. start and end date
 - g. labels: FOR codes, and SEO codes
 - h. privacy level
2. **Researcher** - This includes researcher related information:
- a. researcher related identifiers: ORCID
 - b. research name: first name, last name, title
 - c. institution
 - d. labels: Field of Research (FoR) codes, Socio Economic Objective (SEO) codes, and Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)
 - e. privacy level

The Grants and Researcher data is then pushed into Symplectic Elements data hub (elements-ardc-test-reporting) before exporting into Research Link Australia (RLA) for sharing and collaboration across research sector.

2. Grants Output

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2.1 Data Sources

- **Grants Data:** Information is sourced from the `contracts_grants_main` table for grant details, including **funding amount**, and from the `contracts_grants_investigators` table for investigator data.
- **Researcher Profiles:** Extracted from the `useraccounts` table, particularly focusing on principal investigators' details.
- **Fund Providers:** Anonymised fund provider information is collected from `funds_providers` and processed into unique keys to protect sensitive data.

2.2 Data Processing

- **Grant Titles:** Titles are included only for grants funded by the **Australian Research Council (ARC)**, **Medical Research Future Fund (MRFF)**, or **National Health and Medical Research Council (NHMRC)**. Non-ARC/MRFF/NHMRC grants are assigned a `NULL` title.
- **Anonymised Fund Providers:** Each unique fund provider is anonymised and assigned a key (e.g., SCUFP100). This allows us to track and group fund providers without disclosing sensitive information.
- **Date Standardisation:** Start and end dates for grants are formatted uniformly in the `dd/mm/yyyy` style, ensuring consistency across records.

2.3 Output Structure

The **Grants Output** presents:

- **Grant Title:** Included only for ARC, MRFF, and NHMRC grants.

1. What is ROR? <https://ror.org/about/#what-is-ror>
2. FoR and SEO codes. <https://www.arc.gov.au/manage-your-grant/classification-codes-rfcd-seo-and-anzsic-codes>

- **Principal Investigator:** Investigator details, including ORCID identifiers.
- **Grant Dates:** Start and end dates in dd/mm/yyyy format.
- **Anonymised Fund Provider:** Each fund provider is assigned a unique key (SCUFPXXX).

Griffith University

2.1 Data Sources

- **Grants Data:** Taken from primary RIMS source.
- **Researcher Data:** Taken from primary RIMS source.

2.2 Data Processing

- **Research Data Types:** Records split into primary categories of public grants (ARC, NHMRC, MRFF), commercial and contracts research, donations/philanthropic funding.
- **Organisation Representation:** RoR^[1] codes were used in lieu commercial or branded naming, for specificity and uniqueness.
- **Key Transformations:** Project IDs replaced with GU, to represent partner contribution of records upstream. [ORCID](#) identifiers were mapped internally using staff employment numbers, or manual lookup for external researchers. Order of ORCID identifiers to match projectTeam field.
- **Specific Processing by Category:** For Commercial and Contracts Research, the following specific transformations were applied:
 - Standardise and allocate funder names to one of Partner/Government/University.
 - Remove funding amounts and external participants.
- **Specific Processing by Category:** For Commercial and Contracts Research, the following specific transformations were applied:
 - Anonymise all titles for donations as “Philanthropic Funding”
 - Remove funding amounts and external participants.

2.3 Output Structure

- The Grant Output represents the input structure necessary for ingestion into the Digital Science RLA Hub (middleware) solution. Aligning with the output of UTS.
- Specific output values at each field are dependent on the research data type between public grants, commercial and contracts research and philanthropically funded research. Refer to *DataAugmentationRuleSet.xlsx* for specific guidance at each variable/field.

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2.1 Data Sources

- **Grants Data:**
 - [Grant] – grant related information, including funder details and funding amounts, and grant privacy level – public/private
 - [Grant User Relationship] – user (researcher) and grants relationship information, and privacy level – public/private

2.2 Data Processing

- **Anonymized Fund Providers:**
 - Grants from philanthropic funders are assigned a generic name (auxGrant.funderName='Philanthropic Funder')

2.3 Output Structure

The **Grants Output** presents:

- **Principal Investigator:**
 - Investigator details, including ORCID identifiers.
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3. Researchers Output

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3.1 Data Sources

- **Researcher Data:** Extracted from the `useraccounts` table, focusing on each researcher's name, title, and institutional affiliation.
- **External Identifiers:** Information about researchers' external identifiers ([ORCID](#), Scopus, Researcher ID) is sourced from the `useraccounts_external_references` table.
- **Research Focus: Field of Research (FoR)** ^[2] and **Socio-Economic Objective (SEO)** ^[2] codes are derived from researcher profiles.

3.2 Data Processing

- **External Researcher Identifiers:** The [ORCID](#) identifier is prioritised. If available, **Scopus ID** and **Researcher ID** are also included. The [ORCID](#) profile URL is generated for each researcher.
- **Classification Codes:** FoR ^[2] and SEO ^[2] codes are concatenated into single strings, combining up to three codes for each researcher. This provides a comprehensive overview of each researcher's academic focus and socio-economic impact.
- **Institution Assignment:** A fixed institutional identifier (001xkv632) is assigned to all researchers, indicating their affiliation with Southern Cross University (SCU).

3.3 Output Structure

The **Researchers Output** includes:

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- **Personal Information:** Title, first name, surname, and a fixed SCU email (sdvc@scu.edu.au).
 - **External Identifiers:** [ORCID](#) (with profile URL), Scopus ID, and Researcher ID (if available).
 - **Field of Research (FoR) Codes**^[2]: A list of concatenated FoR codes representing the researcher's focus areas.
 - **Socio-Economic Objective (SEO) Codes**^[2]: A list of concatenated SEO codes representing the socio-economic goals of the researcher's work.
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3.1 Data Sources

- **Researcher Data:** Taken from primary RIMS source.

3.2 Data Processing

- **Researcher Attributes:** Specific attributes associated with a researcher's name such as professional title, contact, and primary persistent identifiers were consolidated and confirmed using [ORCID](#) as the primary reference for attribute information.
- **Researcher Identifiers:** [ORCID](#) identifiers are prefixed with GU to indicate the identifier was contributed from GU. [ORCID](#) was used as the primary cross-check for deduplication and NA value [ORCID](#) identifiers were removed from the dataset.
- **Classification Codes:** For each [ORCID](#) value of the researcher, the Grant table was subset at each row with a matching [ORCID](#) and the corresponding FoR and/or SEO^[2] codes applied to that researcher row. There can be 0 - n number of FoR and/or SEO^[2] codes for each researcher.

3.3 Output Structure

- The **Researchers Output** includes:
 - **Personal Information:** Title, first name, surname, and a fixed GU email.
 - **External Identifiers:** [ORCID](#) (with profile URL).
 - **Institution:** Replaced by respective RoR^[1] code.
 - **Field of Research (FoR) Codes**^[2]: A list of concatenated FoR codes representing the researcher's focus areas.
 - **Socio-Economic Objective (SEO) Codes**^[2]: A list of concatenated SEO codes representing the socio-economic goals of the researcher's work.

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3.1 Data Sources

- **Researcher Data:**

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- o [User] – Researcher related details (e.g. last and first name, title), users privacy label – public/private
- **External Identifiers:**
 - o [User Identifier] – Researcher ORCID, Scopus ID, Researcher ID and Dimensions ID
- **Research Focus:**
 - o [User Label] – researcher FoR codes ^[2], SEO code ^[2] and SDGs

3.2 Data Processing

- **External Researcher Identifiers:**
 - o ORCID identifier is prioritized.
 - o Scopus ID, Researcher ID and Dimensions ID are included if available
 - o Researcher discovery profile URL is included for researchers
- **Classification Codes:**
 - o FoR codes ^[2], SEO codes ^[2] and SDGs are concatenated into single strings.
 - o No maximum number of codes per researcher
- **Institution Assignment:**
 - o UTS identifier: 03f0f6041

3.3 Output Structure

The **Researchers Output** includes:

- **Personal Information:**
 - o Generic email assignment: Researcher title, first name, and surname
 - o Fixed UTS email (rkit@uts.edu.au).
- **External Identifiers:**
 - o [ORCID](#) (with discovery URL), Scopus ID, Researcher ID, and Dimensions ID (if available).
- **Field of Research (FoR) Codes ^[2]:**
 - o A list of concatenated FoR codes representing the researcher’s focus areas.
- **Socio-Economic Objective (SEO) Codes ^[2]:**
 - o A list of concatenated SEO codes representing the socio-economic goals of the researcher’s work.
- **SDGs:**
 - o A list of SDGs representing research sustainable development goal areas (if available)

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